

Effects of Concept-Mapping and Team-Teaching Strategies on Achievement in Biology Concepts Among Secondary School Students in Patigi, Kwara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the effects of concept-mapping and team-teaching strategies on achievement in biology concepts among secondary school students. Quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school two (SSII) Biology students. A researcher designed instrument entitled Biology Achievement Test (BAT) was used for the study. The instrument reliability was done using test re-test method and reliability index of 0.70 was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistic Data collected was analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t-test. The team-teaching group performed better than the concept-mapping group. The findings reveal that team teaching had a more positive effect to concept-mapping in improving student's achievement. Therefore, it was recommended Biology teachers should be encourage to adopt this approach to improve students' achievement in biology

Keyword: Concept-mapping, Team teaching, Achievement, Biology, Secondary school

Introduction

Concept-mapping is a teaching- learning strategy that is embedded with a lot of learners' activities that can trigger critical thinking and cooperation among learners. Schwendimann (2014) defines it as a strategy involving the use of a node-link diagram showing the semantic relationships among concepts. It is a mapping technique that employs the use of nodes, arrows as linking lines and linking phrases to describe the relationship between several nodes, the mapping is aimed at presenting knowledge visually to learner to help organize and structure information in their cognition (Jennings, 2012). The knowledge may be represented using images, photos, colours. to highlight different concepts and their links or by identifying key concepts by name or title. Concept mapping is a teaching and learning approach that promotes meaningful learning through hierarchical presentations of concept by organizing, connecting, and visualizing ideas. It has been shown to be an effective instructional strategy that improves students' academic performance in various subjects. This teaching approach involves the use of graphic organizers to visually represent relationships between concepts or ideas. This strategy has been found to be effective in improving students' understanding and retention of complex information (Mbonu-Adigwe, *et al.*, 2024). Ugwoke and Ude (2022) submitted that concept mapping improved students' understanding and retention of science concept. Similarly, Ahmed, *et al.* (2021) concluded that concept mapping instructional strategy enhanced students' critical thinking skills that are crucial for academic achievement.

Team teaching is an act that occurs in a single physical space for delivering content of instruction involving team of teachers jointly responsible for planning, teaching, assessing and evaluating same group of students (Akpan, *et al.*, 2021). Team teaching is an instructional method involving two or more teachers each with distinctive roles, sharing responsibilities for planning, presentation and evaluation of lessons for a group of learners (Esomonu, *et al.*, 2015). Earlier on, Team Teaching strategy (2023) define team teaching as instructional approach designed to aid cooperation effort among students and teachers in an intellectual exchange that ultimately benefits both parties (Team Teaching Strategy, 2023). Young (2022) defined team teaching as a co-teaching or collaborative teaching that can be used successfully meet the needs of learners with diverse abilities simultaneously in the same classroom. Furthermore, Muza (2021) described team teaching as an instructional teaching approach where group of lecturers work together to plan, conduct and evaluate learning activities of same group of students in a formal setting.

Several studies have been carried out on concept-mapping, among which were: Bull (2025) investigated the impact of curriculum concept mapping on students' perceived academic performance, course material retention, overall perception of curriculum mapping, and self-efficacy and motivation in higher education. The study employed a quasi-quantitative pre-test/post-test design. sample comprised of one hundred undergraduate students. Participants engaged in structured concept mapping activities within a healthcare management course to organize and connect learning objectives, topics, and outcomes. Data collected were subjected to Paired t-tests and linear regression analyses to evaluate changes in students perceived academic

performance and related variables. results demonstrated statistically significant positive improvements in academic performance, retention, overall perception of curriculum mapping, self-efficacy, and motivation. The findings reveal that curriculum concept mapping fosters enhanced comprehension of course content, a deeper connection to learning objectives, and increased confidence in academic capabilities. Abraha (2024) examined the effectiveness of concept mapping in improving students' academic performance using an embedded mixed-methods design. Sample comprised of involved Secondary School's grade 10 biology teacher, students in Srinka. Data were collected using biology achievement tests, interviews, and focus group discussions. The collected data was analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively, and it revealed that concept mapping was more effective in teaching cell division. However, concept mapping was faced with some challenges include practitioners' lack of background experience, time constraints, students' absenteeism, and weak teacher support. Training practitioners, learners' regular attendance and use of context-based materials, time management, and teachers' artistic teaching approaches were suggested as solution strategies. Therefore, responsible bodies are required to create a conducive instructional environment that can scale up practitioners' concept mapping and practice.

Jibril (2024) study examined the effect of using 5E learning-cycle and concept-mapping in teaching genetics to senior school students offering biology. A quasi-experimental was adopted. All Senior School two (SS II) Biology students were the targeted population. A purposive sampling technique was used to select co-educational government secondary schools in three senatorial districts. A Performance Test on Genetics (PTG) was used for data collection. Data collected were analyzed using mean and ANCOVA statistical tool. The findings showed that both learning-cycle and concept-mapping had a positive effect on the performance of the experimental groups than control group. Both learning cycle and concept mapping strategies are not gender biased. Mbonu-Adigwe, *et al.* (2024) study examined the impact of concept mapping instructional strategy on students' academic achievement in basic science in Nigeria. The study was a Quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study was 2,437 junior secondary school two (JSS2), which comprised of 1,334 male and 1,103 female in public secondary schools in Nsukka, Enugu State. The sample comprised 80 JSSII students selected using simple random sampling techniques. The instrument used in the study was Basic Science Achievement Test (BSAT). The research questions were analysed using descriptive statistics while the null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The result show that concept mapping improves students' academic achievement in basic science and no statistically significant improvement observed in students' test scores after the intervention based on gender.

Appaw (2021) compared concept mapping approach and traditional method of teaching biology in Senior High Schools. Two intact classes were randomly selected from five Co-educational Senior High Schools offering elective biology in the New Juaben Municipality. The study was a quasi-experimental research design. The sample size was 105 students. The experimental group 51 students while the control group consisted of 54 students. Means, standard deviations, frequencies, Mann Whitney U, independent sample t-test, paired sample t-test were the statistical tools used for analyses of the data. The results indicated that those instructed with concept mapping did better than those instructed with traditional method.

Iroko and Olaoye (2021) studied the effect of concept mapping on students' academic performance in algebra at senior secondary school level in Ogun state. A quasi-experimental study which comprised of SS II students in Ogun State, 165 students in four intact classes were involved in the study. A-50 item multiple choice achievement test on algebra and 20 item altitudinal questionnaire were used on the selected sample. Data collected were analysed using Mean, Standard deviation and Multivariate Analysis of Covariance (MANCOVA). The findings revealed a statistically significant effect of concept mapping on students' achievement in algebra and no statistically significant effect of concept mapping on students' attitude toward algebra. Wokocha (2020) investigated the effect of concept mapping teaching strategy on students' achievement and retention in Basic Science in Imo State. The experimental group were taught Heat Transfer concepts using the Concept Mapping teaching strategy and control group who were taught using lecture method. Data were analyzed to determine the group equivalence, achievement and retention abilities of the students in the experimental and the control groups using t-test statistics. Findings revealed that Students exposed to Concept Mapping teaching strategy achieved significantly higher than their counterparts taught using lecture method. Also, Students exposed to Concept Mapping instructional strategy retained the learnt concepts significantly better than their counterparts exposed to lecture instructional strategy. There was no significant difference in academic achievement between the male and female students exposed to Concept Mapping.

In additions, Yusuf (2024) compared the impact of single-instructor and team teaching on students' academic performance in Nigeria's South-West region tertiary education. The study question delves into the relationship between teaching styles and students' academic performance using Hayes regression analysis findings from the study reveal that both single-instructor and team-teaching approaches positively affect students' academic performance, but single instructor teaching approach is more effective. Adebisi and Ese (2023) carried out a study on effects of team Teaching on students' academic performance in Basic Science in junior secondary schools in Ado Local government Area, Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study was

a quasi-experimental design. Purposive and stratified random sampling techniques was used to select a sample of 140 JSS II Basic Science students from four junior secondary schools. The instrument for this study was a researcher designed Basic Science Achievement Test (BSAT) and the treatment package entailed Team Teaching Instructional Package (TTIP). The data collected were analysed using t-test and ANCOVA statistics. findings showed that team teaching strategy significantly influenced students' academic performance in Basic Science in junior secondary schools. According Esomonu, et al. (2015) study on team teaching Approach on the achievement of students in English language comprehension and how the effects vary across gender. The study employed quasi experimental design of non-randomized pretest-posttest control group. Intact classes were assigned to the experimental and control groups. A total of 189 students (97 males and 92 females) randomly selected from four public secondary schools constituted the sample. Two research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. Data were collected with same comprehension passage. Data collected were analysed using mean, standard deviation and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses. The major findings showed that the students in experimental group with team teaching approach achieved significantly higher than those of the control group who were taught with single teacher teaching approach. Also, female students in team teaching group achieved significantly higher than their male counterparts.

Students' academic achievement in science subjects particularly biology at Nigerian secondary schools has not been encouraging over the years as reported from senior schools certificate examinations (WAEC Chief examiners reports 2018, 2022,2023) and this has become a cause for concern among educators. Several factors have been identified as contributing to the poor academic achievement among which is teaching methodology. Several studies in science education have been conducted on the use of innovative teaching strategies, such as team-teaching and concept mapping, which have been found to improve students' achievement in science subjects when compared to conventional teachers' method. Several studies have been conducted on concept-mapping and team-teaching both within and outside the country. Some of these studies were reviewed in these studies. However, none of these studies compared concept-mapping and team-teaching approach which was the focus of this research and non were carried in patigi, which was considered in the present study. This study aims to bridge this gap by examining students' achievement using concept mapping and team-teaching strategies in biology because. Due to the strategies potential to improve student outcomes as reported from many researches reviewed

Objectives of the study

1. Is there difference in the achievement of students taught Biology using concept mapping and those taught using team-teaching strategies among secondary school students in patigi, Kwara State?

Research Questions

1. What is the mean achievement score of students taught Biology using concept mapping and those taught using team-teaching strategies among secondary school in patigi, Kwara state?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using concept mapping and those taught using team-teaching strategies among secondary schools in patigi, Kwara state?

Methodology

The research design was a quasi-experimental research design specifically the pre-test, post-test non-equivalent control group design. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school two (SSII) Biology students. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the schools for the study. Biology topics taught for the school term were chosen for the study. The extent of the treatment that was given to these content areas was based on the school scheme of work for the term as extracted from biology curriculum for senior secondary schools. Research designed multiple choice items questions entitled Biology Achievement Test (BAT) was used for the study. The questions went through item analysis to ensure that the items were appropriate in terms of difficulty index and discrimination power. Item analysis was done by trial testing the drafted test item on schools not participating in the study. The Item difficulty and discrimination decisions for the selection of the test questions were based on Abiri (2007). Reliability of the instrument was determined using test-retest method of three weeks' interval on the students of non-participating school. A reliability index of 0.70 was obtained using Pearson's product-moment correlation. Data collected was analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t-test

Results

Data collected were analyzed at 0.05 level of significance

Research Question 1

What is the mean achievement score of students taught Biology using concept mapping and those taught using team-teaching strategies among secondary school in patigi, kwara state?

Table 1: Post test Mean Scores for the Groups

S/N	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1.	Concept-mapping	23	26.69	6.29	Sig.
2.	Team-teaching	29	29.73	10.70	

Table 1 revealed that the mean scores and standard deviation of team-teaching strategy to be 29.73 and 10.70 a which is greater than the mean score and standard deviation of concept-mapping 26.69 and 6.29 respectively. Therefore, there is a difference in the mean scores of the groups in favour of the team-teaching group.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using concept mapping and those taught using team-teaching strategies among secondary schools in patigi kwara state

Table 2: t-test Analysis of Post-test Scores of Students taught using Concept-mapping and Team Teaching

S/N	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	p-value	Decision
1.	Concept-mapping	26.69	6.29	-1.40	0.03	Sig.
2.	Team-teaching	29.73	10.70	-1.25		

The null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using concept mapping and those taught using team-teaching approach was rejected. as p-value is 0.03 ($P < 0.05$) alpha level was obtained, which was significant at 0.05 level. This implies that there exists significant difference between the concept-mapping and Team-teaching achievement mean scores after the treatment in favour of students taught using team teaching strategy among secondary schools in patigi, Kwara state

Discussion of Findings

Research hypothesis seeks to find significant difference in the achievement mean scores of students exposed to concept-mapping instructions and team-teaching shown in table 1, when the mean score of students in both groups were statistically compared, a p-value $p < 0.05$ alpha level was obtained, which implies that there is a significant difference between groups in favour of team-teaching students. Consequently, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the achievement mean scores of students in concept-mapping and team-teaching groups after treatment was not accepted. Therefore, it was discovered that students taught using team teaching strategy had significantly higher academic achievement than their counterpart in concept-mapping approach. This finding affirms the studies conducted on team teaching by Yusuf (2024); Adebisi and Ese (2023) and Esomonu et al,2015.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, there is a statistically significant difference in the achievement of students taught biology concepts using team-teaching strategy as against those taught with concept-mapping. The findings of this study revealed that team-teaching strategy can aid meaningful conceptual understanding and improved achievement in Biology. Therefore, it is concluded team-teaching strategy be utilized in secondary schools for improved achievement in Biology.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made

- i. Team-teaching approach has been proven to improve conceptual understanding of biology by students leading to positive improvement in academic performance. Therefore, teachers should encourage to adopt this approach to better students' achievement in Senior School Certificate Examinations
- ii. Authorities should train Biology teacher through workshops and seminars on how to use team teaching efficiently in teaching and learning in schools

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